

ADVERSE EFFECTS OF PIRFENIDONE AND RAPAMYCIN COMBINATION THERAPY IN IDIOPATHIC PULMONARY FIBROSIS - A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis (IPF) is a persistent, slowly spreading interstitial lung disease characterized by alveolar epithelial damage, excessive deposition of extra-cellular matrix and impaired gaseous exchange, leading to serious respiratory dysfunction and low survival. Existing therapies are intended to reduce the rate of disease progression and enhance pulmonary function. This review evaluates the potential therapeutic potential and safety profile of pirfenidone and rapamycin combination therapy in the management of IPF. Anti-fibrotic and anti-inflammatory pirfenidone suppresses collagen synthesis and fibroblast proliferation whereas mTOR rapamycin regulates immune responses and T-cell proliferation with anti-fibrotic effects also mediated by TGF β 1 /Smad2/3 signalling. Preclinical findings suggest that combination can have greater anti-fibrotic than monotherapy. But side effects such as dermatological reactions, gastrointestinal discomfort,

metabolic changes, fatigue and oedema are also noted which can decrease patient compliance. This review underlines the value of personalized therapy, dose optimization and close attention to monitor adverse reactions. Possible future directions are mass-clinical validation, clarification of toxicity molecular pathways, predictive biomarker discovery and optimization of drug delivery regimens including local or inhaled formulations. Pirfenidone

with rapamycin combination has potential improvement of clinical outcomes and quality of life in patients with IPF with ongoing research, personalized approaches and close pharmacovigilance.

KEYWORDS: Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis, Pirfenidone, Rapamycin, Anti-fibrotic Therapy, Adverse Effects, Combination Therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chronic inflammation is normally the cause of fibrosis which is a long-term immune response that involves tissue remodelling, repair and inflammation.^[1] The common feature of most fibrotic disorders is a continuous irritant that activates growth factors, cytokines and proteolytic enzymes that enhance excessive deposition of extracellular matrix (ECM) especially collagen that gradually disturbs the normal tissue architecture.^[2] Fibroblasts are stromal cells in the shape of fibres that are important because they produce ECM proteins, regulate cytokines and sustain tissue homeostasis.^[3] In activated form, fibroblasts aid in pathological fibrosis which causes dysfunction of organs including nephritis, liver cirrhosis, cardiovascular fibrosis and idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF).^[4]

IPF is a progressive, chronic, interstitial lung disease of unknown etiology which is exaggerated by excessive ECM deposition, accumulation of fibroblasts and myofibroblasts and appearance of honeycomb lung.^[5] The risk factors are smoking, work exposures, infection by viruses or bacteria, age and genetic predisposition.^[6] IPF clinically presents with exertional dyspnoea and dry cough and falls into the groups of idiopathic interstitial pneumonias which is a subset of interstitial lung disease (ILD).^[7] Repeated damage to alveolar epithelial type II cells leads to defective repair,^[10] scarring^[12] and defective gas exchange which causes progressive respiratory insufficiency.^[13] In this review, the dermatological unwanted events associated with the use of pirfenidone and rapamycin as a combination therapy have been discussed as well as the mechanisms behind the reactions. Figure 1 and 2 represents how the normal lung modulates to the disease.

Figure 1: Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis.

Figure 2: Interstitial lung disorder.

2. Pathophysiology

IPF has no known cause. Other scientists opine that it can be autoimmune, and in persons prone to it, it is precipitated by bronchial viral infections that mimic the lung proteins. The primary agent causing tissue destruction in the lung and resulting in fibrosis is chronic inflammation. Neutrophils and macrophages come and settle in the alveoli releasing growth factors and cytokines that activate fibroblasts. These fibroblasts synthesize collagen, making the lungs stiff, impairs lung functioning and distorts the usual lung architecture (Figure 4).^[14]

Alveolar epithelial cells may be abnormally stimulated by small injuries, genetic or epigenetic alterations resulting in the release of profibrotic growth factors, chemokines, and enzymes.^[15] Short telomeres or telomerase gene mutations are associated with people having higher susceptibility to developing IPF due to multiple episodes of alveolar cell injury. Damaged alveolar cells secrete the cytokine TNF-alpha, IL-1 and CCL2 that attract additional cells and aggravate tissue injury. TGF-b is secreted by dysfunctional endothelial and epithelial cells and stimulates the multiplication and transformation of fibroblasts to

myofibroblasts, the primary collagen-producing cells.^[14] Aging-related changes, like DNA damage, defective autophagy, and mitochondrial problems, also contribute. One of the greatest risks is the process of telomere shortening which leads to cell senescence and is particularly common in familial IPF.^[15]

Figure 3: Schematic view of IPF.

3. Pirfenidone

Pirfenidone (PFD) is an anti-proliferative, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant therapy to treat idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), a chronic progressive interstitial lung disease.^[18] It decelerates the forced vital capacity (FVC) loss by preventing profibrotic mediators, including TGF- β , collagen production, and fibroblast growth and stimulates tissue repair.^[19] PFD is predominantly excreted via CYP1A2 and 70-80 percent of the drug is found in the urine as 5-carboxy-pirfenidone.^[23] In clinical practice, PFD enhances vital capacity^[22], decreases fibrosis^[33], and delays the disease progression in IPF patients.^[22]

3.1 Mechanism of Action

PFD lessens proinflammatory cytokines such as the TNF- α ^[24], IL-1 β ^[24], IL-6^[24], and interferon- γ ^[24]. It regulates Th1/Th2^[24], suppresses dendritic cell-T cell activation^[24], macrophage-mediated inflammation^[24], and neutrophil migration.^[24] PFD inhibits myofibroblast differentiation through Smad3^[23], Akt^[35], and p38^[60] inhibition, HSP47

expression inhibition^[35], and regulates matrix metalloproteinases^[23], platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF)^[23], and fibroblast growth factor (FGF) pathways.^[23]

3.2 Adverse Effects of Pirfenidone

Pirfenidone lowers the IPF progression or mortality rates by about 35 per cent and postpones the reduction in lung functionality indices e.g. VC and FVC.^[21] Almost all patients have some level of adverse reactions but they are quite mild to moderate most of the time and can be treated by changing the dose, discontinuing temporarily, and treating the symptoms.^[21] There are serious complications like liver dysfunction, hepatic tumor and respiratory insufficiency that are reported to be rare.^[21]

3.2.1 Gastrointestinal Reactions

The most common adverse events when using pirfenidone are gastrointestinal (GI) adverse events. Such symptoms as anorexia, nausea, dyspepsia, and diarrhoea are commonly reported.^[21,57] Anorexia or nausea were found in 24 out of 41 patients (58.5%), and diarrhoea occurred in 1 patient (2.4%) in one clinical cohort.^[25] Such GI effects are dose-limiting and are a primary reason to stop treatment.^[25]

3.2.2 Skin-Related Reactions

Photosensitivity, skin rash, pruritus, and, more infrequently, photophobia is also linked to pirfenidone.^[21,53] Photosensitivity had been present in 5 patients (12.2) and 2 patients had allergic skin reactions (4.9) in a clinical cohort.^[25] The skin appearances are usually reversible under sun protection, topical therapy or adjustment of doses.^[53]

3.2.3 Other Adverse Events

A clinical cohort reported fatigue in 2 patients (4.9%), photophobia in 1 patient (2.4%), and vertigo in 1 patient (2.4%).^[25] During therapy, laboratory results, including high liver enzymes are also observed.^[21] Other non-GI, yet relevant adverse effects are weight loss and general malaise.^[47]

3.2.4 Incidence in Clinical Studies

In a 2011 study on advanced IPF (PAS Programming to Provide Optimal Research) 91 of 144 patients (63.2) had adverse drug reactions (ADRs) of special interest, including 213 events in total. The most prevalent (43.8) were GI events, then 20.8 weight loss, 19.4 fatigue, and 16.0 skin/photosensitivity reactions.^[47] In pooled analyses, 693 out of 1009 patients (68.7)

reported ADRs. GI events were 38.3, skin / photosensitivity reactions 29.0, fatigue 24.2, and weight loss 16.1.^[47]

3.2.5 Treatment Discontinuation and Time Course

In a different study, 15 out of 41 patients (34.1%) discontinued treatment mainly because of anorexia and nausea.^[25] Discontinuation rates were less in larger, integrated safety analyses where 1.4% of discontinuation was because of rash, 1.9 because of fatigue and 2.7 because of nausea.^[48] The majority of ADRs are reported in the first month of treatment, especially in GI and skin events, although the rate decreases substantially after six months and stays low at a maximum of 54 months.^[48]

4. Rapamycin

4.1 General Safety Profile

The mTOR inhibitor rapamycin (sirolimus) is considered to be well-tolerated, but the number of patients who exhibited some type of adverse reaction is high. In a single controlled trial, 27 subjects (96 percent) had at least one adverse event, but primarily they were minor and the total frequency was not significantly different than placebo.^[26]

4.2 Gastrointestinal and Metabolic Effects

ADRs commonly reported involve gastrointestinal effects like nausea, diarrhoea, and abdominal pain.^[26] Hyperlipidemia is common and serum lipid may be high in patients up to 30 percent needing statin treatment.^[27] Other associated metabolic disorders are diabetes or hyperglycemia and high blood pressure.^[28]

4.3 Hematologic Effects

Use of Rapamycin has been associated with cytopenias such as anemia, leukopenia, and thrombocytopenia.^[26,27] Long-term therapy has been found to result in decreases in hemoglobin, mean corpuscular volume, and mean corpuscular haemoglobin.^[27]

4.4 Skin and Mucoctaneous Reactions

Cutaneous ADRs are less prevalent, but of clinical interest. These are aphthous ulcers, acnesiform dermatitis, folliculitis, erythematous maculopapular rash, stomatitis and onychopathy.^[28] During the initial month of treatment, oral ulcers (59%), nausea (32%), and diarrhoea (24) were most prevalent, however, after one year they decreased to 15, 7 and 2 respectively.^[44] On the other hand, acne (17%), oedema (12%), and menstrual irregularities

(7%) were augmented with the long period of treatment.^[44] Severe mucocutaneous reactions, like generalized pruritus and ulcerating rash are uncommon, but can require discontinuation.^[28,44]

4.5 Respiratory and Other Complications

Rapamycin-treated patients had fewer respiratory side events than placebo, such as cough, dyspnea and infections.^[26] Nevertheless, cases of pneumonitis have also been reported with sirolimus therapy, delayed wound healing, nephrotoxicity, proteinuria and peripheral oedema.^[28,42]

4.6 Treatment Discontinuation

The side effects necessitated sirolimus discontinuation in about 33 percent of patients following 8-9 months of treatment, mainly because of intolerance of gastrointestinal, metabolic, or dermatologic complications.^[27]

5. PRENIFIDONE AND RAPAMYCIN COMBINATION THERAPY

Fibroblasts of patients with IPF were cultured and stimulated with TGF- β , pirfenidone, and rapamycin, in which case the joint treatment without TGF- β resulted in a substantial decrease in tenascin-c levels.^[18] Combination of Pirfenidone and rapamycin showed an additive inhibitory effect on CD4 and CD8 T-cell proliferation than by either drug only.^[30] TGF- β signalling plays a key role in wound healing since it has been reported that using Smad3 deletion and Tgfr2 knockout mouse models showed changes in re-epithelialization, collagen organization, and macrophage recruitment.^[43] Pirfenidone exhibited low apoptosis induction at 1 mM but the 10 mM with 10% DMSO was an effective apoptosis inducer.^[45] Rapamycin and Pirfenidone proved to be more effective than monotherapy in BLM-induced lung fibrosis models, whereby they combined to increase survival, decrease fibrosis and inflammation, and inhibit TGF β 1/Smad2/3 signalling.^[46] A rash occurrence of grade 1-2 of 22.7% was reported in the clinical evidence and strategies against selectivity of TGF- β which is combined with mTOR inhibitors can further restrain fibroblast activation.^[49,59] The expression of TGF- β 3 was highly expressed in the keratinocytes indicating the necessity of Smad2/3 control in epidermal homeostasis and effective wound re-epithelialization.^[50,51] Nevertheless, sirolimus treatment can be linked with the maculopapular rash, and close attention should be paid to both the levels of rapamycin and drug interactions because of its low therapeutic index.^[54]

Drug/Combination	Adverse Drug Reactions
Pirfenidone	Gastrointestinal: nausea, diarrhea, anorexia, dyspepsia. Dermatological: photosensitivity, allergic reactions, skin rashes, skin hypersensitivity, subcutaneous tissue, abnormalities, pruritus Neurological: acute exacerbation Hepatic: liver tumor, liver dysfunction Others: photophobia, vertigo, weight loss, fatigue, dizziness
Rapamycin	Gastrointestinal: oral aphthous ulceration, nausea, diarrhea, stomatitis Dermatological: acne, peripheral edema, wound healing complications, skin rashes, pruritus Pulmonary: pneumonitis Hematology: anemia, decreased mean corpuscular hemoglobin, hypertension, thrombocytopenia, leukopenia, Others: menstrual abnormalities, diabetes, dyslipidemia, proteinuria, nephrotoxicity, cell apoptosis
Pirfenidone + Rapamycin	Gastrointestinal: nausea, diarrhea Dermatological: skin rashes, pruritus, maculopapular rash, tissue edema Others: fatigue

Future Perspective

The future of pirfenidone-rapamycin combination therapy in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) will require taking advantage of the advanced technologies to utilize the full efficiency of this treatment and reduce the toxicity. Pharmacogenomics and biomarker-driven stratification integration may facilitate treatment response monitoring in real-time, accurate patient selection, and decrease the adverse drug reactions and enhance patient adherence. Targeted nanoparticles, hydrogel-based and inhalable formulations are nanotechnology-based delivery systems capable of increasing bioavailability of a local drug in the lung, but with reduced systemic exposure. Machine learning and artificial intelligence can also be used to hasten drug-response forecasting, refine dosing code, and discover new synergistic targets. These new technologies, combined with organoid and single-cell transcriptomics platforms to simulate fibrotic processes, have the potential to transform the pirfenidone-rapamycin therapy into a personalized, adaptive and safer therapy and eventually redefine the IPF therapeutic landscape.

CONCLUSION

IPF is an incurable deadly condition with few therapeutic options, and combining pirfenidone with rapamycin presents a promising approach with pirfenidone suppressing fibroblast proliferation, collagen deposition, and pro-inflammatory signalling and rapamycin suppressing mTOR-mediated cell growth, immune activation and fibrotic remodelling. Such a dual mode can be synergistic in its effect to slow the disease progression, but adverse drug effects like photosensitivity, rash, nausea, diarrhoea, fatigue, oedema and metabolic disturbances pose a considerable obstacle to sustained compliance. Taking into consideration the patient-related parameters such as age, comorbidities and genetic predisposition, which influence efficacy and tolerability, personalized treatment with the help of pharmacogenomics, biomarker surveillance, and close dose control is essential. Development of predictive biomarkers, large-scale clinical trials, mechanistic study of ADRs and improved delivery systems (e.g. inhaled formulations) should be a priority in future research to improve benefit-risk ratio. Finally, the concept of the combination therapy of the drugs pirfenidone and rapamycin has a high potential in enhancing the results of IPF, as long as their translation is directed by personalized medicine and strict safety oversight.

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